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Cultural Tapestry of the Nagas: Indigenous Beliefs and Practices in Easterine Kire's *Don't Run, My Love*

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Abstract:

Northeast Indian Writing in English is an emerging area of study. These writings are enriched with the cultural distinctiveness of various tribes living in the area. The topographical features contributed to the immense variety of the region. Environmentally rich, the region connects the worlds of human beings and nature. Easterine Kire, the first fiction writer in English from Nagaland, is recognized for her portrayal of the history and culture of the Angami Nagas in her writing. Her novel, *Don't Run, My Love* (2017), tells the story of a widowed mother, Visenuo, and her daughter, Atuonuo, set in the cultural context of traditional Naga village life. The story gives the upheavals in the life of a young woman through various activities and encounters. This article is intended to point out the cultural elements of the Nagas presented in the text. It also analyses the spiritual world of the Nagas reflected in the novel.

Keywords: Northeast, culture, indigenous, spirits, Nagaland.

Northeast India has a unique history and culture. The region, collectively referred to as the "Northeast", comprises eight states: Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Manipur, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, and Tripura. Numerous indigenous tribes inhabit the various parts

of the topographically diverse region. There are mountains of multiple heights, valleys, rivers, and forests with innumerable species of plants and animals. Cultural and linguistic diversity have given each tribe a unique identity. In the pre-independence period, this area was isolated from the outside world. As a result, each tribe developed its distinctive ways of administration and living. The entire area is linked to mainland India through a narrow Siliguri corridor commonly referred to as the “chicken’s neck” due to its distinctive shape. The tribes living in different states began to receive modern education after the British arrived and introduced the modern school system in some areas, with the help of missionaries.

Whatever they had in the form of stories, songs, or poems was passed down through oral traditions. Nagaland, Mizoram, Arunachal Pradesh, and Meghalaya had their literary traditions rooted in orality. Legends and folklore were passed down orally from one generation to the next. Priyanka Kakoti has opined, “There was a vibrant oral tradition among many communities of the Northeast, mostly the hill tribes” (Kakoti 16). Indeed, the tribes considered spoken words to be more authentic than written words. The rich tradition of oral storytelling became fundamental to how Naga communities preserved their past, maintaining cultural practices and values that might otherwise have been lost to time.

The academic interest of scholars from various parts of the country grew at the end of the twentieth century due to the emergence of a large body of writing in English from Northeast India. Universities such as North Eastern Hill University, Nagaland University, Mizoram University, and Manipur University have nurtured and disseminated the literary culture of the region. Writers and scholars associated with the literature departments of the universities produced a considerable amount of writing. They have been nationally and internationally recognized. Noted writers are Mamang Dai, Jahnabi Barua, Mitra Phukan, Tamsula Ao, Aruni Kashyap, Easterine Kire, Monalisa Changkija, Janice Pariat, Anjum Hasan, Mona Zote,

Kynpham Sing Nongkynrih, Robin S. Ngangom, and many others. Mamang Dai and Easterine Kire have won the Sahitya Akademi Award for their literary works.

This article intends to focus on the literary representation of the indigenous culture of Nagaland. The indigenous people living in this state are known as the Nagas. There are many groups of Nagas with their distinctive cultural ethos. However, some fundamental similarities can also be found in most of the groups, which bring them together under the identity known as the Nagas. Easterine Kire, in her book *Walking the Roadless Road* (2019), provides detailed descriptions of the sixteen major tribes of Nagaland. These are the Angami, Ao, Chakhesang, Chang, Dimasa Kachari, Khiamniungan, Konyak, Kuki, Lotha, Phom, Pochury, Rengma, Sangtam, Sumi, Yimchunger, and Zeliang. They were treated as uncivilised by the British. Education and outside knowledge were unknown to them because they had an oral culture only. Their traditional knowledge is rich with ecological and ethical values.

Easterine Kire is a prominent writer from Nagaland. She has written over twenty books, including fiction, nonfiction, poetry, and children's literature. She was born in 1959 in Nagaland. She was educated in a convent school and did higher studies at North Eastern Hill University. She has done her Ph.D. from Savitribai Phule Pune University. Her writings focus on the history and culture of the people of Nagaland. Although Northeast India is known for its political instability, writers often make this their theme; however, Easterine Kire focuses on the beauty of life and nature. She writes about the villages, societies, and spirituality of remote areas in Nagaland, where nature and supernatural elements reign with human beings. Her novels, such as *When the River Sleeps* (2014), *Journey of the Stone* (2021), and *Spirit Nights* (2022), represent the spiritual world of the Nagas.

The Nagas are primarily dependent on agriculture for their livelihood, and rice serves as the staple food of Naga communities. Therefore, agricultural activities reflect their philosophy of life. As agriculturalists, they must understand nature and its environmental

fluctuations to grow and harvest crops. This necessity has led them to be very hardworking, and at the same time, it teaches them to work together and support one another. Communal bonding has been built on this foundation. Naga spiritual life reflects their deep connection to agriculture, where seasonal farming cycles interweave with religious practices and community beliefs. N.K. Das, in his article “Cosmology, Ecology, and Spirituality: Reappraising Stone Culture, Genna Tradition, and Ancestor Veneration among the Naga Tribes”, has noted, “The Naga Spiritual Worldviews and the cosmovision encode ethical practices, taboos, and the knowledge systems, which are historically linked with farming practices and agrarian rituals” (46-47).

Don't Run, My Love (2017) tells the story of a widowed mother, Visenuo, and her daughter, Atuonuo. Visenuo deliberately chose to live in a village. The women and children in Naga Village work hard in the fields. Agriculture was a vital means of livelihood. Both of them work in the field, as it is harvesting time. They bring loads of grains using indigenous techniques. They spend time in the field huts, return to the village, converse with the neighbours, cook and eat traditional food, and observe festivals and rituals. Thus, they live contentedly. It is a world filled with twittering birds, scampering squirrels, shadows of old fig trees, barking deer, waylaying spirits in darkness, and the crowing of village roosters. One day, they meet a young man named Kevi, who helps them carry loads of grain. He also secretly offered them meat, as he was a skilled trapper and hunter. Kevi wanted to marry Atuonuo. However, she rejected him. Kevi becomes a weretiger and attacks Atuonuo. This indigenous magical practice of the weretiger is a part of Naga folklore. The mother and daughter go to meet the seers to rid themselves of Kevi. Ultimately, Kevi, as a weretiger, again attacked Atuonuo when they were returning from the village of the seers, and this time, the woodsman Kyo killed him. It was the evil in man that ended.

At the beginning of the novel, Kevi voluntarily helps Visenuo carry a heavy load of grain, as he sees that she is struggling with it. She also, in turn, thanks him by inviting him to eat something at her house. The tribal people show their mutual acknowledgement in various ways. One way to express gratitude is to offer to share something to eat. Therefore, Atuonuo offers, “You must stay and share our food” (*Don’t Run, My Love* 3). Kire comments on this: “Offering a meal was the traditional way to thank somebody who had given unsolicited help” (*Don’t Run, My Love* 3). Using the third-person point of view, the writer highlights the ritualistic significance of each activity in the novel. Regarding marriage, the girls are supposed to marry around eighteen. They have the freedom to refuse any suitor if she does not like him. Tuonuo refused “a couple of young men”. The boys are required to propose to a girl in order to get someone to agree to marry.

Working in the field and returning home in time before darkness engulfs the area is the schedule of activities for the villagers. The fields and forest become fearful in the darkness. The people are superstitious, and stories of spirits hover around the villages. Additionally, wild animals emerge to attack the villagers. So, it is always imperative to be back home before evening. Atuonuo and her mother were anxious about returning. Kire has said, “They were both relieved that they had completed their journey without encountering any wild animals or spirits” (*Don’t Run, My Love* 14). This reflects the psychological fear of the place. They are worried about nature’s vagaries that might harm the harvest. Their thoughts revolve around the secure harvest of the grains. Sometimes frost and rain would ruin the harvest if timely action is not taken.

Easterine Kire is concerned with the beautiful aspects of tribal life. She believes that tribal society possesses an inherent quality in terms of imparting human values through its social and cultural practices. The positive aspects of tribal living have been appreciated and

depicted with utmost care in her novels. The primitive practices of the people have been imbued with sweetness. The communal bonding and respect for one another make their life fulfilling.

The fields, forests as hunting grounds, homes, food, and interaction with neighbours occupy the ideological space of the Naga people. Atuonuo and Visenuo spend a lot of time transporting grains from the fields. It consumes a significant portion of their time. They carry the load of grains themselves. In the fields, they have a hut for rest. However, before nightfall, they return to the village. This journey forms the motif of village life. The villagers cope with the appearance of the wild animals and spirits. Most villagers are skilled hunters. The meat of the hunted animal is shared with others. The villagers are always conscious of acknowledging any help from anyone. This aspect makes them good human beings. Visenuo is eager to identify the person who provided them with a good portion of the meat, consisting of an animal's leg. Visenuo comments, "We have to find out who our benefactor is and try to compensate him somehow" (*Don't Run, My Love* 21).

The tribal people live very close to nature. They make everything organic in their life. Every house maintains a kitchen garden in the backyard, where they grow spices like ginger, garlic, chili, basil, and lentils. They use them while cooking food items. Even traditional medicinal plants grew there naturally. The interesting thing is that they were aware of the medicinal benefits of those plants and took care of them. Kire has commented on the knowledge of Visenuo regarding the plant, "In one corner was a large patch of *japan nha*, Crofton weed. They had not uprooted it because it was said to be effective against malaria and stomach aches" (*Don't Run, My Love* 27). In the novel, *Don't Run My Love*, Atuonuo has a kitchen garden. They use earthen pots for cooking meat, which makes the meat tastier. Kire also comments in the novel, "Nevertheless, Visenuo insisted on using it as meat cooked in an earthen pot tasted far better than meat cooked in an aluminium pot; people would say there was something about mud pots that added a pleasing flavour to the meat" (*Don't Run, My Love* 27). Here, the writer

upholds the traditional culture of the Nagas. The aluminium pot is a modern invention, but the earthen pot is more eco-friendly and is used by the tribal people. The gradual transition of the society is also indicated here through the mention of a choice between an aluminium pot and an earthen pot.

The novel is set in the village named Phesa or Kija. It is a typical Naga village. The structure of the village has *thelhou*, a community house, a village gate, and other typical places. In the novel, the conversation between Visenuo and her daughter Tuonuo points out the positive aspects of the community house: “The boys who have been brought up in that tradition learn things about our culture” (*Don’t Run, My Love* 18). In traditional Naga society, education was passed down through oral storytelling. Young boys gathered in the community house called *kichuki* in the case of Angami Nagas. Different Naga tribes had different names for the community house. Kire, in this novel, presents the importance of the community house in imparting moral values to young boys through the stories of history. The Nagas were brave tribes and loved warfare. They were noted for their headhunting practices. Kire has indicated in this novel that they were humans, and naturally, they had fears in their minds too. In the community house, young boys were taught to be courageous.

Each Naga village was well protected both physically and spiritually. In the novel, *Don't Run My Love*, Easterine Kire presents a village of the Seers, which is structurally not very different from other villages. The gate of this village is adorned with significant cultural symbols that reflect the Naga people's belief system. As a symbol of bravery, the figures of warriors were carved in the gate. The gate is made up of a single large wooden block. Symbols of fertility and wealth were represented in the carvings, including hornbills, female breasts, animal heads, and human figures hunted by enemies. In another novel, *Journey of the Stone* (2021), Kire has also written about the rituals the Naga villagers perform while building a village and its gate called *kharu* (*Journey of the Stone* 30). These rituals are believed to protect

the villagers from the evil spirits entering the village. The gate represents the male gender, featuring carvings of shields and spears.

The tribal people celebrate the harvest festival with various forms of entertainment. They perform some rituals to propitiate the deities of crops. They strictly maintain the traditional taboos during the festival. One of the rituals mentioned by Visenuo to her daughter is *Kevakete* in local terms, in which “the mother of all the household has to refrain from eating rice; she eats only boiled lentils” (*Don't Run, My Love* 52). Every member of the household eats only after the mother finishes eating. These rituals, according to Visenuo, bring blessings from the supernatural spirits: “These rituals transfer blessings upon our harvest” (*Don't Run, My Love* 52). Kire has commented on the maintenance of taboos and their significance: “...the Harvest Festival had its own list of taboos, each intended to propitiate the spirits and prevent the destruction of the grain that had been brought into the granaries” (*Don't Run, My Love* 52). Thus, the primary concern of the people is to protect the grains at any cost, and in this, they depend on nature and beliefs in spirits who will undoubtedly help them in life. Among the taboos is the prohibition of eating grasshoppers and dragonflies because they are supposed to eat grains if angered.

The novel also depicts their belief in *tekhumevi* or “weretiger”, in which a man's spirit becomes a tiger, as well as their dependence on seers. In other novels, Kire has highlighted the deep-seated belief in the Seers, who can foretell many things through their foresight. People go to seers to learn about the causes of dangers and the mysteries of life. The village of Meriezou is renowned for its popular seers. Everyone is searching for the village's location. Seers are wise persons who can answer many mysteries with a strange power of knowledge. People believed in them. By telling things, the seers control the behaviour of the people.

Visenuo and her daughter visit the village of seers to find a solution to the attack that Atunuo faced in the field hut. Kevi was taken as a weretiger, and they wanted to kill a weretiger.

However, the seer told them that they cannot kill a life. The concept of weretiger is a cultural practice. People believe that a man can cross over into the spirit world. By crossing it, the man gets knowledge of the future of the warriors. The seers have access to the spirit world. Pfenno informs Visenuo, “The man becomes the tiger. Moreover, we call them *tekhumevimia*. The crossing they make into the spirit world gives them the power to predict who will be victorious in war and other such things” (*Don't Run, My Love* 102). Here, two types of *tekhumevi* are seen. One who voluntarily becomes *tekhumevi* as a gift, and another is inherited as a legacy from their fathers. The second one is a curse. Both males and females can become *tekhumevi*.

The novel *Don't Run, My Love* is significant to study in order to understand the nuances of the Naga cultural practices. Beginning from the basic life activities, marriage rules, hospitality rules, rituals related to agricultural activities, the fears of fields, hard work, taboos, festivals, belief systems, the most noted practice of weretigers, dependence on seers, village structure, status of women, spirit encounters and such identity markers of the Nagas have been presented in the novel through a few characters like Visenuo, Atuonuo and Kevi. It is worth noting that the references in the story reflect the traditional life of a Naga village. Atuonuo is a girl who appears to be unaware of the changes that occurred in Nagaland during colonization and afterward. Visenuo remarks that she only knows the things the village has taught her since childhood, and she tries to pass them on to her daughter (*Don't Run, My Love* 18). No trace of Christianity is visible in it. It remains a charming, mystical presentation of traditional rural Nagaland.

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